

A new chemosensor selective for Cu²⁺ ions through fluorescence quenching approach applicable to real samples[†]

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Abstract : A new salen type Schiff base H₂L has been developed as an efficient Cu²⁺ ions selective turn-off chemosensor through metal chelation (1 : 1) in 1 mM HEPES buffer-ethanol (50%, v/v) solution at 25 °C. The probe (H₂L) was characterized by thorough physicochemical and spectroscopic studies, and the fluorescence quenching process due to the selective addition of Cu²⁺ ions has been established by detailed Stern-Volmer plot considering both static and dynamic quenching phenomena along with the theoretical study. The probe has good photostability with pH insensitivity. The probe exhibited significant sensitivity and selectivity to Cu²⁺ ions over other competitive metal ions due to significant binding affinity ($k = 1.51 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$) of the probe towards Cu²⁺ ions as low as 10.55 nM. This probe is also efficient to estimate Cu²⁺ ions in real samples including natural water.

Keywords : Chemosensor, Cu²⁺ ion, fluorescence quenching, Stern-Volmer plot, strip test, water sample.

Introduction

The development of selective and sensitive chemosensors for the detection of metal ions has received considerable attention because of their important roles in medicine, living systems and the environment¹. Among the transition metal ions of interest, copper is the third most abundant trace element after Fe³⁺ ions and Zn²⁺ ions in biological and ecological systems²; and it is playing the imperative biochemical functions ranging from bone formation and cellular respiration to connective tissue development³ and many physiological processes in the human gene expression, nervous system and the structural and functional enhancement of proteins⁴. Several transcription factors, zinc-copper superoxide dismutase, lysyloxidase and cytochrome-C oxidase require copper for maintaining their activities⁵. Again, excesses or deficiencies of copper causes imbalance in cellular processes resulting in pathogenesis. Accordingly, the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has set the maximum allowable level of copper in drinking water at 20 μM⁶. Nevertheless, copper contamination and its potential toxic effects on human beings continue to be challenging problems throughout the world. As a result, it is

significant to develop rapid, highly sensitive and selective methods for Cu²⁺ ions determination.

The existing methods of selective detection of trace level copper ions including electrochemistry⁷, atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS)⁸, and inductively coupled plasma mass spectroscopy⁹ are usually complicated, time-consuming and costly too. Fluorimetric method, in contrast, has many advantages comprised of good sensitivity, non-destructive and capability of real-time detection; as a result highly selective and sensitive chemosensors for detection of biological relevant metal ions and molecules are very useful tools for chemistry, biotechnology and medical diagnostics¹⁰.

Currently, several fluorescent probes for Cu²⁺ ions detection have been reported¹¹, but in most of the cases structurally complicated systems of large molecular weight with the interference of other transition metal ions such as Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Ag⁺, Pb²⁺ and Hg²⁺ ions. Herein, we report a fluorescent tetradentate *salen-type Schiff base* as a Cu²⁺ ions selective probe developed by tuning its fluorescent properties through chelation with copper(II) ion considering the versatile applications of salicylidenes¹² in different fields. This probe showed highly photostable

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

blue fluorescence, and exhibits good sensitivity and selectivity for the detection of Cu^{2+} ions over other transition metal ions.

Considering the above facts and the versatile applications of salicylidenes in different fields, a tetradentate chelating Schiff base has been established as Cu^{2+} ions selective chemosensor by tuning its fluorescent properties through chelation with copper(II) ion. Herein, we report a novel *salen*-type Schiff base as a fluorescent probe for Cu^{2+} ions detection. This probe shows highly photostable blue fluorescence, and exhibits good sensitivity and selectivity for the detection of Cu^{2+} ions over other transition metal ions.

Experimental

Materials :

High-purity HEPES, *o*-phenylene diamine, 4-diethylamino-2-hydroxy-benzaldehyde and cupric chloride dihydrate were purchased from E. Merck. Solvents used were spectroscopic grade. All metal salts were used as either their nitrate or their chloride salts. Other chemicals were of analytical reagent grade and used without further purification except when specified. Milli-Q, $18.2 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}^{-1}$ water was used throughout all experiments.

Synthesis of the probe (H_2L) :

To an ethanolic solution (25 mL) of benzene-1,2-diamine (216 mg, 2 mmol) 4-*N,N*-diethyl-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (770 mg, ~ 4 mmol) in ethanol was added dropwise with stirring at room temperature, and the resulting solution was then refluxed for 8 h (vide Scheme 1). During reflux the color of the solution turned into deep brown. Then the volume of the solvent was reduced to one third of the original using rotary evaporator. The resulting viscous mass was dissolved in dichloromethane and passed through a column packed with celite to remove the im-

purities. Finally the collected filtrate was dried in rotary evaporator to obtain the probe H_2L as brown colored solid.

$\text{H}_2\text{L} \cdot \text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$: Yield : 60%; m.p. ($^\circ\text{C}$) : 74 ± 2 ; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$, 3455; $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$, 1629; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 500 MHz, δ ppm) : 0.997–1.114 (12H), 3.372–3.387 (8H), 6.19 (1H, s), 6.29–6.311 (1H, d), 6.599–6.617 (2H, t), 7.021–7.040 (2H, d), 7.769–7.791 (1H, d), 8.561 (1H, s) and 13.296 (1H, s) (viz. Fig. S2); ESI-MS : $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, m/z 459.2740 (100%) (Calcd. m/z , 458.2682; where M = molecular weight of H_2L).

Preparation of L-Cu complex :

To a solution of H_2L (459 mg, 1 mmol) in dry ethanol (25 mL) was added cupric chloride dihydrate (170 mg, 1 mmol) and the resulting solution was stirred for 12 h (vide Scheme S1). The resulting solution was then kept aside overnight for evaporation. Green colored solid resulted, which was filtered, washed with diethyl ether and vacuum dried.

L-Cu complex. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{32}\text{CuN}_4\text{O}_2$: Yield : 40%; m.p. ($^\circ\text{C}$) : 190 ± 2 ; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$, 1611; ESI-MS : $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, m/z 520.1857 (10%) (Calcd. m/z , 519.1921; where M = molecular weight of L-Cu complex).

Physical measurements :

A Shimadzu (Model UV-1800) spectrophotometer was used for recording electronic spectra at room temperature. FTIR spectra were recorded using Perkin-Elmer FTIR model RX1 spectrometer preparing KBr disk. Electrospray ionization (ESI) mass spectra were recorded on a Qtof Micro YA263 mass spectrometer and a Bruker Avance DPX 500 MHz spectrometer for recording ^1H NMR spectra using DMSO- d_6 solution. A Systronics digital pH meter (Model 335) was used to measure the pH of the

Scheme 1. Synthetic strategy of the probe (H_2L).

Mondal *et al.* : A new chemosensor selective for Cu²⁺ ions through fluorescence quenching approach *etc.*

solution and the adjustment of pH were done using either 50 mM HCl or NaOH solution. Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was performed by using Merck F254 silicagel-60 plate. Redox potentials were measured in CHI620D potentiometer in DMF using TBAP as supporting electrolyte at room temperature.

Methods :

The stability constant K of the complex was determined with a linear relationship by the Benesi-Hildebrand method¹³.

$$1/(F_x - F_0) = 1/(F_{\max} - F_0) + (1/K[C])(1/(F_{\max} - F_0))$$

where F_0 , F_x and F_{∞} are the emission intensities of the organic moiety considered in the absence of Cu²⁺ ions, at an intermediate Cu²⁺ ions concentration, and at a concentration of complete interaction, respectively, and where K is the binding constant and $[C]$ is the cation concentration. The fluorescence quantum yields (Φ) were estimated by integrating the area under the fluorescence curves with the equation :

$$\Phi_{\text{sample}} = \Phi_{\text{ref}} \times \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{ref}} \times A_{\text{sample}} \times \eta_{\text{sample}}^2}{\text{OD}_{\text{sample}} \times A_{\text{ref}} \times \eta_{\text{ref}}^2}$$

where A is the area under the fluorescence spectral curve, OD is the optical density of the compound at the excitation wavelength and η is the refractive index of the solvent used. The standard used for the measurement of fluorescence quantum yield was anthracene ($\Phi = 0.27$ in ethanol)¹⁴.

Theoretical calculation :

DFT calculations of the probe (**H₂L**), and its corresponding complex **L-Cu** were done with the help of Gaussian-09 software over a Red Hat Linux IBM cluster with the B3LYP/6-31G(d,p)¹⁵ functional model and basis set.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

The synthesis of the fluorescence probe was shown in Scheme 1. Combination of *benzene-1,2-diamine* with *4-N,N-diethyl-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde* in dry ethanol resulted in the respective probe **H₂L**. The obtained **H₂L** was readily soluble in all common solvents. The chemical structure and purity of the probe were confirmed by FT-IR, ESI-

MS (Fig. S1) and ¹H NMR spectra (Fig. S2). The ESI-MS spectrum shows a principal peak at $m/z = 459.2740$ with 100% abundance ($M+H^+$), which is in consistent with the **H₂L** molecular formula. The monomeric **L-Cu** complex was obtained in good yield from the reaction of copper(II) chloride with the organic moiety (**H₂L**) in 1 : 1 molar ratio in ethanolic medium with prolonged stirring in room temperature (viz. Scheme S1, Supporting information). The solubility of the complex was quite good in all common organic solvents. In the IR spectrum of complex **L-Cu**, the peak corresponding to $\nu_{C=N}$ has been shifted to 1610.66 cm⁻¹ from this peak observed in the IR spectrum of free **H₂L** (1629.21 cm⁻¹); this observation is in agreement with the chelation of N donor of C=N to Cu²⁺ ions. The peak at $m/z = 520.1857$ with 10% abundance ($M+H^+$) observed in ESI-MS spectrum (viz. Fig. S3) is in support of molecular formula of **L-Cu** complex, which is comparable with reported copper(II) complexes of the similar salen-type Schiff bases¹⁶. It is noteworthy that this complex showed no fluorescence. Fig. S4 shows the excitation and emission spectra of probe in 1 mM HEPES buffer-ethanol (50%, v/v) solution. The maximum excitation and emission are at 345 nm and 400 nm, respectively, showing a large Stokes shift of 55 nm.

Stability on fluorescence of the probe (**H₂L**) :

The fluorescence intensity of the probe (**H₂L**) was systematically examined in the pH range from 4.0 to 11.0 using 1 mM HEPES buffer-ethanol (50%, v/v) solution (Fig. S5), which clearly indicates that the fluorescence intensities of **H₂L** are insensitive to pH variation of this range. The photostability was also investigated by irradiating the probe solution in 1 mM HEPES buffer-ethanol (50%, v/v) solution under a xenon light source (Fig. S6). After excitation at 345 nm (30 s intervals for each time), no apparent change in fluorescence intensity was observed, suggesting the good photostability of the probe which ensures the reliability of the fluorescence measurements.

Spectral responses of the probe against Cu²⁺ ions :

The interaction between the probe and Cu²⁺ ions was thoroughly examined with UV-Vis absorption spectra. For the UV-Vis experiments, the absorption spectrum of free probe solution was first measured, as shown in Fig. 1. It can be seen that there is no apparent characteristic absorption band above 450 nm. When Cu²⁺ solution was

Fig. 1. The UV-Visible absorption spectra of 10 μM H_2L in 1 mM HEPES buffer-ethanol (50%, v/v) solution and the change after adding different amounts of Cu^{2+} ions.

gradually added into the probe solution, a new absorption band at 480 nm appeared and gradually increased as the amount of Cu^{2+} ions increased. When more than 1 equiv. of Cu^{2+} ions was added, the new absorption band at 480 nm almost remained unchanged, suggesting the formation of a 1 : 1 stoichiometric copper(II) complex, which is confirmed by Job's plot that was obtained from the emission spectra of the probe in the presence of Cu^{2+} ions.

The fluorescence property of probe and its response to Cu^{2+} ions were examined in 1 mM HEPES buffer-ethanol (50%, v/v) solution (Fig. S7). The free probe (H_2L) showed a maximum fluorescence peak at 400 nm. With the addition of Cu^{2+} , the emission at 400 nm decreased greatly in a proportional way, which could be due to the formation of a complex L-Cu . With the increase of Cu^{2+} ions concentration, the fluorescence intensity continuously decreased and finally became non-fluorescent within a very short time period. More Cu^{2+} ions showed no further effect on the fluorescence of 10 μM H_2L , as displayed in Fig. 2, which is also reflected in the values of the calculated quantum yields (Φ). The value of Φ decreases by *ca.* 150 times due to the addition of Cu^{2+} ions from $\Phi = 0.15$ to $\Phi = 0.001$.

Analytical figure of merits :

Initially, the fluorescence intensity gradually decreased as the concentration of Cu^{2+} ions increased. When the concentration of Cu^{2+} ions equaled to the probe concentration, the fluorescence intensity reached minimum and kept constant at higher Cu^{2+} ions concentrations, imply-

Fig. 2. Fluorescence spectra (λ_{ex} , 345 nm) of 10 μM H_2L with various concentrations of Cu^{2+} ions in 1 mM HEPES buffer-ethanol (50%, v/v) solution.

ing the 1 : 1 stoichiometric reaction between the probe and Cu^{2+} ions. The results clearly suggest that this probe has a high sensitivity for Cu^{2+} ions in 1 : 1 stoichiometric reaction (Fig. S8) due significant binding affinity (binding constant $1.51 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$) of the probe to the Cu^{2+} ions (Fig. S9).

The detection limit of the fluorescence spectral measurements, as calculated on the basis of $3\sigma/S^{10c,17}$ (where σ is the standard deviation of the blank solution and S is the slope of the calibration curve; Fig. 3), showed a detection limit of approximately 10.55 nM for Cu^{2+} ions, which is far lower than the maximum level for copper of 20 μM in drinking water from EPA guidelines.

Fig. 3. Calibration graph of H_2L (10 μM) in 1 mM HEPES buffer-ethanol (50%, v/v) solution upon addition of Cu^{2+} ions.

Mondal *et al.* : A new chemosensor selective for Cu^{2+} ions through fluorescence quenching approach *etc.*

Selectivity study :

The solutions of K^+ , Na^+ , Ba^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Hg^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ag^+ , Pb^{2+} and Cu^+ ions were used to investigate the metal ion selection of probe (H_2L), as shown in Fig. S10. 50 μL of metal ions in aqueous solutions were added into 10 μM of H_2L solution, followed by recording the fluorescence spectra and emission intensity of the resultant mixture. It can be seen that adding other metal ions does not quench the fluorescence under the same conditions. In contrast, Cu^{2+} ions showed a significant quenching effect on the fluorescence of the probe (H_2L) with almost 100% quenching of the fluorescent intensity. This clearly indicates the probe's good selectivity for Cu^{2+} ions over other cations. The selectivity difference can be ascribed to the different binding abilities of these metal ions to the probe.

Interference study :

To validate the method, interference study of the probe (H_2L) for Cu^{2+} was carried out by adding a mixture of metal ions (100 equiv. of K^+ , Na^+ or 50 equiv. of Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Ni^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Hg^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and Cu^+ ions with 1 equiv. of Cu^{2+} ions) to 10 μM probe (H_2L) solution (Fig. 4). The addition of the mixtures decreased the fluorescence intensity of the probe in the same manner as the Cu^{2+} ions, indicating that the quenching effect of Cu^{2+} ions was not affected by other coexisting metal ions. These results clearly suggest that the probe (H_2L) shows a high selectivity toward Cu^{2+} ions and high anti-interference ability against other coexisting metal ions.

Fluorescence quenching mechanism :

The fluorescence quenching of (H_2L) by incremental addition of Cu^{2+} ions could be caused by the binding of Cu^{2+} ions of paramagnetic nature at the recognition unit,

Fig. 4. Fluorescence responses of H_2L solution (10 μM) to Cu^{2+} ions (10 μM) in the presence of other metal ions.

promoting intramolecular energy or electron transfer (Scheme 2). From the experiment results, it can be seen that there is no overlap between the absorption spectrum of Cu^{2+} ions and the emission spectrum of the probe, ruling out the possibility of fluorescence resonance energy transfer. Therefore electron transfer (ET) may be the dominant reason for the fluorescence quenching. The chelated copper(II) centre may attract electrons from the excited phenolate moiety and quench the fluorescence. So it is rational to propose that the quenching effect can be attributed to the electron transfer (ET) between the chelated copper(II) centre and the excited organic moiety.

Reversibility study :

This can be supported by the following control experiment. When ethylene diamine tetraacetic acid (EDTA) was added into the mixture of H_2L and Cu^{2+} ions, the fluorescence was recovered to its initial intensity of the probe (H_2L) as we expected (Fig. S11). This is because EDTA has higher binding affinity than the probe and removes the copper metal centre from the non-fluorescent complex to form more stable EDTA-Cu complex,

Scheme 2. Plausible sensing mechanism.

releasing the fluorescent probe ($\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{L}$). In addition, Cu^{2+} ions could not quench the fluorescence of the probe ($\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{L}$) in the presence of EDTA, which suggests that EDTA competes with the probe to chelate with Cu^{2+} ions. These results further confirm that the fluorescence quenching by Cu^{2+} ions is attributed to the formation of the complex $\mathbf{L}\text{-Cu}$ as proposed in Scheme 2, which was confirmed by ESI-MS and FT-IR results which is consistent with the chemical structure of the complex proposed in Scheme 1 (Supporting information).

Electrochemical study by cyclic voltammetry :

To elucidate the understanding of the electrochemical behavior the complex ($\mathbf{L}\text{-Cu}$), the metal centred redox property of the complex was examined by cyclic voltammetry using a Pt-wire working electrode in DMF and in presence of $[\text{n-Bu}_4\text{N}]\text{ClO}_4$ as the supporting electrolyte (Fig. 5). The complex ($\mathbf{L}\text{-Cu}$) displayed a one electron equivalent quasi-reversible voltammogram corresponding to $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ couple having $i_{\text{pc}}/i_{\text{pa}} \approx 1$ with the difference in the potential values only depending upon the oxidation state of the copper ion. The $E_{1/2}$ value of -199.5 mV ($\Delta E = 117$ mV) for this couple in $\mathbf{L}\text{-Cu}$ in cathodic side was obtained. From this study the formation of $\mathbf{L}\text{-Cu}$ complex was also established.

Fig. 5. Cyclic voltammogram (scan rate 100 mV/s) of ($\mathbf{L}\text{-Cu}$) Cu-complex in DMF solution containing 0.1 M TBAP, using platinum working electrode.

Density Functional Theoretical (DFT) studies :

To describe the understanding of the electronic disposition and the ground state character of $\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{L}$ with Cu^{2+} ions DFT calculations were performed to attain the

optimised geometry of $\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{L}$ and complex $\mathbf{L}\text{-Cu}$ (Fig. S12). From this study it is clear that the energy gap between HOMO-LUMO in complex $\mathbf{L}\text{-Cu}$ is 3.3255 eV is reasonably lower than that of free $\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{L}$ (3.7014 eV) giving rise a more stable species produced by the formation of chelate complex.

Fig. 6. Fluorescence quenching of $\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{L}$ solution ($10 \mu\text{M}$) due to the addition of Cu^{2+} ions.

Stern-Volmer plot :

In this graph (Fig. 6), I_0/I was plotted against adding Cu^{2+} ions concentration. At the beginning when Cu^{2+} ions added (upto $5.0 \mu\text{M}$) to the solution of $\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{L}$ ($10 \mu\text{M}$) the graph linearly increased. After that the graph dramatically bent towards Y-axis upto $10 \mu\text{M}$ copper(II) addition. More addition of Cu^{2+} ions marginally changed the fluorescence intensity. This observation can be explained by the two different quenching phenomena, one is static and another is dynamic. When below $5.0 \mu\text{M}$ Cu^{2+} ions was added to the solution of $\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{L}$, static quenching was observed due to ground state complex formation between $\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{L}$ and Cu^{2+} ions. But when a considerable amount of complex was formed in the solution then newly added Cu^{2+} ions and already formed $\mathbf{L}\text{-Cu}$ complex both played the quenching process simultaneously. As a result of this fact, further addition of Cu^{2+} ions ($> 5.0 \mu\text{M}$) showed dynamic quenching process and on a whole the probe ($\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{L}$) quenched through both static and dynamic processes¹⁸.

Spike and recovery test of Cu^{2+} ions in tap water :

Spike and recovery test was conducted in tap water to examine whether there is any positive or negative inter-

ference in real drinking water samples. We first examined the effect of tap water on the fluorescence stability and found no quenching effect. The local tap water was filtered first through 0.45 μm Supor filter store move any particulate suspension. The recovery study was carried out on the mixture of water and ethanol (1 : 1, v/v) which were spiked with 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 μM Cu^{2+} ions. Each concentration was done in triplicate and the average was presented with relative standard deviation. The fluorescence spectra of H_2L to different spiked tap water sample were shown in Fig. 7. From this, it can be seen that the method has a good recovery at the concentrations tested, suggesting no serious positive or negative interferences for selectively and sensitively determining Cu^{2+} ions in real water samples.

Fig. 7. The fluorescence spectra of H_2L (10 μM) in 1 mM HEPES buffer-ethanol (50%, v/v) solution to different spiked tap water samples (2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 μM Cu^{2+} ions) (λ_{ex} = 345 nm).

Strip test :

To validate the use of H_2L for the selective detection of Cu^{2+} ions, test strips were prepared by immersing filter papers in a water and ethanol (1 : 1, v/v) binary solution of H_2L (1.0 mM) followed by exposure to air until completely dry. Intriguingly, the generated fluorescence color (Fig. 8A) was quenched immediately from blue to colorless once the test paper is immersed in an aqueous solution of Cu^{2+} ions (1.0 mM) observed under UV light (Fig. 8B). The same procedures were done for Cu^{2+} ions and different cations (Fig. 8C). The immersion of these test strips in the solution mixture of other cations

Fig. 8. Photographs of H_2L on test strips : (A) only H_2L , (B) after immersion into water solutions with Cu^{2+} ions, (C) after immersion into water solutions with other cations, and (D) after immersion into water solutions with Cu^{2+} ions and other cations under irradiation at 345 nm.

(5 mM) did not affect any color change i.e. the blue color of the strips remained unchanged. When these strips were immersed in the solution of Cu^{2+} ions again, the color quenched as above immediately (Fig. 8D). Thereby chemosensor H_2L exhibits excellent fluorescence sensing performance, which will be very useful for the fabrication of sensing devices with fast and convenient detection for copper and cations.

Conclusions

A new photostable Schiff base (H_2L) as a fluorescent probe (H_2L) has been synthesized and characterized and it selectively senses Cu^{2+} ions over other competitive transition metal ions in 1 mM HEPES buffer-ethanol (50%, v/v) solution at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ based on ‘turn-off’ process. The detection limit of the probe for Cu^{2+} ions was found to be 10.55 nM, which is far lower than the maximum level for copper of 20.0 μM in drinking water as per EPA guidelines. The efficacy of the probe to measure Cu^{2+} ions in real water samples has also been successfully justified. In addition, test strips based on H_2L were fabricated, which could serve as a practical fluorescent sensor to detect Cu^{2+} ions in field measurements or in test kits.

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Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at <http://www.indianchemsociety.in>

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